

The Role of the Higgs Field in Time Relativity, Dynamism and Entropy

Anubhav Thakur

December 3, 2024

Abstract

This paper aims to establish a link between the Higgs field with Dynamism, Entropy, and Time Relativity by proposing the idea that the higgs field is directly related to the motion, entropy and the perception of time. The main concept behind this idea is that the higgs field is directly related to why energy is dynamic by proposing that there is a feedback loop between the higgs field and particles which gives them mass and dynamism which causes entropy and gives us the perception of time. This theory proposes that the higgs field is interconnected with spacetime and gives us the missing link to what causes energy to be dynamic and why time exists.

1 Introduction

The Higgs field is a fundamental quantum field that is spread all over the universe and exists through spacetime. It was first proposed as part of the standard model of particle physics. It gives particles mass through a process called spontaneous symmetry breaking without this field particles will not have mass and the universe will be unable to form the structures necessary for the existence of matter. This theory provides a very new idea that ties together the higgs field with the dynamic nature of particles which causes entropy and entropy and dynamism creates change in particles which we perceive as time. The theory claims that when a particle interacts with the higgs field the particle reshapes the structure of the higgs field by interacting with it this disbalance in its structure causes the higgs field to also interact with the particle creating a feedback loop between the particle and the higgs field which causes particles to be dynamic in nature now due to this feedback loop the dynamic particles and the higgs field gives rise to entropy the entropy of the particles in the universe then gives rise to changes which gives us the perception of time this theory aims to explain how the higgs field interacts with spacetime which gives rise to time dilation and the reliveness of time depending on how the particles are interacting with the higgs field in here.

2 Theoretical Framework

2.1 Mass and the Higgs Field

This theory proposes that the relationship between the total amount of mass relative to another will affect how time will play out between the two in an object with a larger mass

compared to a smaller mass the object with the larger mass will interact more with the higgs field causing its perception of time relative to an object with lower mass to be slower as its interaction with spacetime via the higgs field is more which causes its entropy to be slower creating a slow passing of time compared to an object with lower mass. Photons for example do not interact with the higgs field at all and time does not exist for them in the same way particles with mass do because they interact with spacetime via the higgs field which gives them mass, motion, entropy, dynamism and time.

2.2 Dynamism and the Higgs Field

This theory tries to of propose the idea that dynamism is not a fundamental property of particles but its due to their interaction with the higgs field by causing a disruption in the symmetry of the higgs field which again interacts with the particles creating a feedback loop this ensures that the particles when interacting with the higgs field will always stay dynamic and have properties of entropy and also the preception of time which is caused due to changes that can be observed giving us the perception that is time.

2.3 Entropy and Higgs-Spacetime Interaction

This theory proposes that entropy is a byproduct of the feedback loop between particles and the higgs field which makes systems dynamic giving rise to disorganization over time. This proposes that the higgs field is directly interconnected with spacetime and the interaction of objects with mass with this field gives us time and the speed of an object will also determine its rate of change relative to another the idea is that objects with faster speeds the higgs field interact with it more aggressively effectively slowing down its entropy and perception of time compared to with objects with slower speeds which have a reduced amount of higgs field pressure allowing entropy and the arrow of time to go faster then objects with highere speeds which have a lower rate of entropy

3 Conclusion

To summarize this theory proposes that dynamism entropy and time are by the byproducts of the feedback loop that happens with the interaction of particles with the higgs field and photons bypass the field entirely which means they dont have entropy and do not have time.

References

Higgs, P. W. (1964). Broken Symmetries and the Masses of Gauge Bosons. *Physical Review Letters*, 13(16), 508–509. <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.13.508> (The foundational paper that introduced the Higgs mechanism.) ATLAS Collaboration. (2012). Observation of a New Particle in the Search for the Standard Model Higgs Boson with the ATLAS Detector at the LHC. *Physics Letters B*, 716(1), 1–29. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.physletb.2012.0> (The paper reporting the discovery of the Higgs boson, confirming the existence of the Higgs field.) Carroll, S. M. (2010). *From Eternity to Here: The Quest for the Ultimate Theory of Time*. Dutton. (A book exploring the nature of time and its relationship to physics, entropy, and the universe.) Zee, A. (2010). *Quantum Field Theory in a Nutshell*.

Princeton University Press. (An accessible explanation of quantum field theory, including the Higgs field.) Einstein, A. (1916). The Foundation of the General Theory of Relativity. *Annalen der Physik*, 354(7), 769–822. <https://doi.org/10.1002/andp.19163540702> (The foundational paper on general relativity, relevant for discussions of spacetime.) Penrose, R. (2010). *Cycles of Time: An Extraordinary New View of the Universe*. Knopf. (Explores the arrow of time and entropy in the context of cosmology.) Hawking, S. W., Penrose, R. (1970). The Singularities of Gravitational Collapse and Cosmology. *Proceedings of the Royal Society A: Mathematical, Physical and Engineering Sciences*, 314(1519), 529–548. [<https://doi.org/10.1098/rspa.1970.002>]